

Metadata

Information on study	
Study	EU FAR Database - EU Funds Absorbed by Romanian Municipalities

Bibliographic Information	
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Study Title	EU FAR database - EU Funds absorbed by Romanian Municipalities 2016-2022
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Principal Investigator Reference	
Principal Investigator (Person Reference)	Anca Monica Marin
Principal Investigator (Institution Reference)	Research Institute for Quality of Life, Romanian Academy
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Information on Study: Content Information	
Abstract	The database contains information about the EU funds as expenditures in the local budget (as opposed to allocating funds) reported by each locality (municipality) in their annual budget execution reports. The data is processed by the authors, based on the information published by the Ministry of Development, Public Works and Administration, Directorate for Local Fiscal and Budgetary Policies, Romania.
Keywords	EU funds, local government, LAU, Romania, programming period, open science, urban, rural, municipalities, public administration

Information on Study: Methodical Information	
Time Method	annual, 2023
Reference Period	2016-2022 (for 2014-2020 programming period)
Last Update	December 2023 (second upload)
Unit of Analysis	LAU 2
Type of Sampling Procedure	all population

Information on Study: Legal Information	
Data Access	open access
Language of Data Access	English

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Database description

The cumulative EU funds for the period of 2014-2020 represent financial data from the local budget execution, as published by the Ministry of Development, Public Works and Administration, Directorate for Local Fiscal and Budgetary Policies.¹ The data management process included merging all the information for all the localities in Romania by assigning correct unique identification codes (LAU codes)² for all municipalities for all the examined years. The category of EU funds from the programming period of 2014-2020 is registered as a distinct category in the local budgets' execution starting from 2016. The implementation of EU-funded projects from this period registered a delay associated with the approval of new operational programs, management authorities, etc. The budgetary classification used for this category by the Ministry of Public Finance includes EU funds from all funding sources, including those from the European Regional Development Fund, European Social Fund, Common Agricultural Policy, and other external funds, such as the Norwegian financial mechanism. Notably, all the information in the database presents payments (executed budget) and not allocations.

The data published by the Ministry of Development, Public Works and Administration are reported in lei (national currency). The process of data management converted the sums for each year in euro, based on the Euro/EUR exchange rates - annual data.³ Afterwards, the sums in euro have been converted in euro at constant 2010 prices, based on the price index, implicit deflator.⁴

The next step included computing the constant euro per inhabitant for each year. The population information comes from the National Institute of Statistics.⁵ For the year of 2022, the information on population comes from the Population Census of 2021. As a final step, all the data in euro at constant 2010 prices per inhabitant have been summed up to

¹ http://www.dpfb.mdrap.ro/sit_ven_si_chelt_uat.html

² From 2017 only LAU (see <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/nuts/local-administrative-units>)

³ Eurostat indicator [ERT_BIL_EUR_A]. This means that each sum in lei has been divided to the annual value corresponding to Romanian leu from the corresponding Eurostat indicator – average value.

⁴ Eurostat indicator [NAMA_10_GDP], Price index (implicit deflator), 2010=100, euro, for updating the database for 2022 data has been extracted on November 20th, 2023. Data for computing first version of the EU FAR database has been extracted on September 29th, 2022 and the values used for computing the sums correspond to the dates of extraction. This means that each sum converted in euro has been multiplied with 100 and then divided to the annual value from the corresponding Eurostat indicator.

⁵ National Institute of Statistics, Tempo online database – Pop107D, Population by home, at 1st of January, by age group, gender, counties and localities. This means that each sum converted above in constant euro has been divided by number of inhabitants.

have a total sum of all EU funds absorbed by each municipality in Romania for the programming period of 2014-2020.⁶

⁶ The database presents the computed sums, but also data in euro (at 2010 constant prices) to enable, for different research purposes, to use the information expressed only in volumes of euro, without ratio per inhabitant.

For comparative purposes, the variable on total sum of EU funds, expressed as euro, in constant prices per inhabitant,⁷ is indicated to be used. However, if interested only in the total volume of EU funds absorbed by each municipality, by year or as a total sum, the rest of the variables can be used.⁸ Adding on, affiliation of each locality to NUTS 3 and NUTS 2 levels can also be used to generate relevant statistics for these two levels – counties and development regions in Romania.

Limitations

The way budgetary data are reported currently does not allow for a differentiation between separate lines of EU funding. Additionally, although the database offers disaggregated data at the locality level, it does not include all eligible entities able to absorb EU funds at the municipality level, such as small and medium sized enterprises, farmers, or research institutes. Moreover, it is not possible to have a distinction by operational programme, priority axis, thematic objective and measure. Furthermore, the funds spent from the first programming period for Romania, namely, 2007-2013, are registered in a separate category, starting from 2009, yet they have not been processed into the sums publicly displayed in this database.

In addition, for the year of 2022, EU funds from PNRR (National Recovery and Resilience Plan) have been reported in the local budgets execution database. Therefore, the sums reported in EU FAR database do not represent the entire volume of EU funds absorbed in the year of 2022, but only the ones corresponding to the analyzed programming period (2014-2020).

Concerning the level of territorial analysis, the structure of local public administration is different in Bucharest, when compared to the rest of urban and rural municipalities. The municipality of Bucharest comprises one general mayoralty and six district mayoralties, which function as separate units and report separately the EU funds absorbed. Consequently, if the analysis is conducted by locality (and not by mayoralty), the sums for Bucharest include the entire volume of funds from the general and district mayoralties.

Next steps

The project team envisages data updates once the information becomes available. In this respect, the third version of the database, which will be available next year will also include the volumes of expenditures corresponding to 2023. Therefore, next year's update of EU FAR database will be able to report on the entire volume of the expenditures from the programming period of 2014-2020. EU FAR database has been integrated into various EOSC ([European Open Science Cloud](#)) services and will continue to make full use of the professional opportunities offered by EOSC. In addition, the support offered by [Research Data Alliance](#) (RDA) for developing the first steps of EU FAR database represents a further potential platform for collaboration with FAIR data specialists to look for common tools, approaches and data models.

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⁶ Variables name in the database: [SUM_EU_2016_2021_inhab], [SUM_EU_2016_2022_inhab].

Variable Description

Variable name	Definition	Notes
SIRSUP	Unique Code Identifier for Territorial Administrative Units (LAU 2 Code)	For more information on LAU codes in Romania, see: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/nuts/local-administrative-units
LOCALITY	Locality Name (LAU 2)	For more information on LAU names in Romania, see: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/nuts/local-administrative-units
COUNTY	County Name (NUTS 3)	For more information on NUTS 3 codes in Romania, see: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/nuts/local-administrative-units
Development Region	Development Region Name (NUTS 2)	For more information on NUTS 2 classification in Romania, see: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/nuts/background
SUM_EU_2016_2022_inhab	Total sum of EU funds absorbed by each locality for the programming period of 2014-2020, in the period of 2016-2022 (in euro, at constant 2010, prices/inhabitant)	Computed based on the information published in local budgets execution data, information for 2016-2022. For more information on data processing, see Database description.
SUM_EU_2016_2021_inhab	Total sum of EU funds absorbed by each locality for the programming period of 2014-2020, in the period of 2016-2021 (in euro, at constant 2010 prices/inhabitant)	Computed based on the information published in local budgets execution data, information for 2016-2021. For more information on data processing, see Database description
SUM_inhab_2016	Total sum of EU funds absorbed by each locality in 2016 (in euro, at constant 2010 prices/ inhabitant)	Computed based on the information published in local budgets execution data and annual population data from the National Institute of Statistics. For more information on data processing, see Database description
SUM_inhab_2017	Total sum of EU funds absorbed by each locality in 2017 (in euro, at constant 2010 prices/ inhabitant)	Computed based on the information published in local budgets execution data and annual population data from the National Institute of Statistics. For more information on data processing, see Database description
SUM_inhab_2018	Total sum of EU funds absorbed by each locality in 2018 (in euro, at constant 2010 prices/ inhabitant)	Computed based on the information published in local budgets execution data and annual population data from the National Institute of Statistics. For more information on data processing, see Database description
SUM_inhab_2019	Total sum of EU funds absorbed by each locality in 2019 (in euro, at constant 2010 prices/ inhabitant)	Computed based on the information published in local budgets execution data and annual population data from the National Institute of Statistics. For more information on data processing, see Database description
SUM_inhab_2020	Total sum of EU funds absorbed by each locality in 2020 (in euro, at constant 2010 prices/ inhabitant)	Computed based on the information published in local budgets execution data and annual population data from the National Institute of Statistics. For more information on data processing, see Database description
SUM_inhab_2021	Total sum of EU funds absorbed by each locality in 2021 (in euro, at constant 2010 prices/ inhabitant)	Computed based on the information published in local budgets execution data and annual population data from the National Institute of Statistics. For more information on data processing, see Database description
SUM_inhab_2022	Total sum of EU funds absorbed by each locality in 2022 (in euro, at constant 2010 prices/ inhabitant)	Computed based on the information published in local budgets execution data and annual population data from the National Institute of Statistics (Census data). For more information on data processing, see Database description
SUM_2016_2022_cst	Total sum of EU funds absorbed by each locality for the programming period of 2014-2020, in the period of 2016-2022 (in euro, at constant 2010 prices)	Computed based on the information published in local budgets execution data, information for 2016-2022. For more information on data processing, see Database description
SUM_2016_2021_cst	Total sum of EU funds absorbed by each locality for the programming period of 2014-2020, in the period of 2016-2021 (in euro, at constant 2010 prices)	Computed based on the information published in local budgets execution data, information for 2016-2021. For more information on data processing, see Database description
SUM_2016_cst	Total sum of EU funds absorbed by each locality in 2016 (in euro, at constant 2010 prices)	Computed based on the information published in local budgets execution data. For more information on data processing, see Database description
SUM_2017_cst	Total sum of EU funds absorbed by each locality in 2017 (in euro, at constant 2010 prices)	Computed based on the information published in local budgets execution data. For more information on data processing, see Database description
SUM_2018_cst	Total sum of EU funds absorbed by each locality in 2018 (in euro, at constant 2010 prices)	Computed based on the information published in local budgets execution data. For more information on data processing, see Database description
SUM_2019_cst	Total sum of EU funds absorbed by each locality in 2019 (in euro, at constant 2010 prices)	Computed based on the information published in local budgets execution data. For more information on data processing, see Database description

SUM_2020_cst	Total sum of EU funds absorbed by each locality in 2020 (in euro, at constant 2010 prices)	Computed based on the information published in local budgets execution data. For more information on data processing, see Database description
SUM_2021_cst	Total sum of EU funds absorbed by each locality in 2021 (in euro, at constant 2010 prices)	Computed based on the information published in local budgets execution data. For more information on data processing, see Database description
SUM_2022_cst	Total sum of EU funds absorbed by each locality in 2022 (in euro, at constant 2010 prices)	Computed based on the information published in local budgets execution data. For more information on data processing, see Database description

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